

METHODOLOGY FOR TEACHING INFORMATION CULTURE TO STUDENTS IN THE SYSTEM OF HIGHER EDUCATION

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Annotation. This article analyzes the political, social, commercial or cultural interests of information transmitters in the context of the formation, critical reception and creation of Information Culture to students in the higher education system, identification of information sources.

Key words: Information, culture, literacy, internet, media, media space, social media, media text,

Introduction

Today, information attacks carried out over the Internet have become part of the national security strategy of every country in the world, and it has been named cyber security. After all, the merging of the virtual and real world, the misunderstanding of the real world by young people through the virtual world, the dissemination of information that appears positive at first glance, but has a negative effect on the human mind, by various negative forces and currents. It is no secret that it is increasing. There are increasing opinions that it is necessary to make the population media literate in order to prevent these negative aspects affecting the life of the society. Today, media literacy is taught as a separate subject in the complex of humanities in Great Britain and Australia, while in Finland it was included in the curricula of secondary schools in 1970, and in higher education institutions in 1977. In the 1990s, media literacy in the country was replaced by the concept of media education. In Sweden, it has been taught as a separate subject in educational institutions since 1980. In the 1990s, there were attempts to conduct scientific research of media education in Russia, and the researches of O. Baranov, S. Penzin, A. Fyodorov, A. Sharikova and others can be an example of this. In 2002, a course on media education was opened for higher educational institutions of pedagogy. In 2005, the textbook "Media education" was created under the auspices of UNESCO, and the website of film education and media pedagogy was launched in Russia.

Uzbekistan is rapidly integrating into the world information space. Citizens of the country today have the opportunity to receive unlimited information and information collected by the world community. The quality of the information we receive and use has a great impact on our life choices and social and political activities. Today, the reforms in the information environment, cooperation with the press "correctly define the priority aspects of relations" and the economic

mechanisms of control over the activities of mass media (mass media), the closure of information sources, as well as the known actions of authorities and administrative structures to the editors. aimed at eliminating level pressures.

Results and discussion

At this point, the Parliament is working on the adoption of a number of laws that ensure "openness and transparency of the activities of executive authorities, the reforms implemented in our country, and the internal and external policies of the state." In particular, on May 5, 2014, the law "On the openness of the activities of state authorities and management bodies" was adopted in our republic. There is no doubt that this law will serve to make the national information space more transparent, expand it, and enrich the image of Uzbekistan in the global information space, as well as the content, form and methods of national content. The development of techniques and technologies during the last twenty years has led to an incomparable expansion of the media, information sources and information suppliers (libraries, archives, the Internet, etc.) and has made it possible for citizens to use and exchange its huge volume. As a result, citizens have the opportunity to evaluate the reliability of this information, to fully exercise their rights to freely express their opinion.

The Declaration expresses the importance of media literacy and information culture in providing opportunities to effectively seek, evaluate, use, and create information to achieve personal, social, professional, and educational goals in all areas. Media literacy and information culture is one of the basic human rights that encourages the increase of social activity of all peoples in the world of digital information and digital technologies. The task of media and information literacy is to deliver this knowledge to users. Media and information literacy includes the following key concepts:

- a) functions of media, library, archive and other information services in a society developing in the traditions of democracy;
- b) conditions for mass media and information services to effectively perform these functions;
- c) methods of evaluating the quality of performance of these functions through the provided content and services.

These concepts, in turn, allow users to consciously interact with communication and information channels. The knowledge gained through media and information literacy should develop critical thinking in citizens and create the basis for them to demand high-quality service from the media and other information providers.

So why is media literacy necessary?

First of all:

- To understand the content and essence of the reforms implemented as a full-fledged, active citizen of our legal democratic society;
- formation of skills for sorting daily information transmitted and received through mass media;
- Avoiding control of the human mind by information and making the right decision in any situation;
- To be able to analyze positive or negative changes of a person under the influence of visual images and to "read" invisible information given under visual messages;
- Analyzing the nature of textual communications given through mass media;
- It is necessary to find answers to the questions of where, by whom and for what purposes the information is being transmitted, whose interests it reflects.

According to Wikipedia, "Media literacy is a set of skills that enable people to analyze, evaluate, and create different forms of media and messages. A person with high media literacy will be able to easily notice which source is reliable and which source is spreading false news.

Media literacy allows consumers to analyze what forces media to engage in propaganda, censorship, or bias in information and public programs, as well as to understand structural elements such as media owners and their funding model.

It is impossible to develop the education system without wide introduction of modern information and communication technologies. In this regard, the modern higher education system promotes the use of information and communication technologies as an important tool for the professional activity of future specialists.

In order to increase the efficiency and quality of the educational process, it is important to create favorable conditions for the use of information and communication technologies, to create software tools that automate the educational process, and to provide them with multimedia instructional manuals and methodical manuals.

A very large volume of information provided by electronic resources such as some electronic directories, encyclopedias, internet portals can also distract attention during the educational process. Human short-term memory provides very limited possibilities. When the reader is shown different types of

information at the same time, he skips important information in order to follow other information and becomes distracted from one type of information.

Research on information literacy shows that technological skills are better developed in young people than in adults. This situation is related to the fact that modern young people are familiar with technical innovations since childhood, and use them to collect, process and transmit information for personal or social purposes. Nevertheless, young people face certain difficulties in evaluating the accuracy and reliability of evidence.

Conclusion

During the formation of the global information society, media and information literacy is an important factor that ensures national development, increasing social activity and responsibility of every citizen for the future of the country, active participation of the population in democratization processes, protecting our national spirituality from informational threats, analyzing information while acquiring theoretical knowledge, to determine the source and purpose of information, the used media methods, to understand the need for information culture in the context of globalization, to know the role of mass media as a means of increasing the media literacy of the population, to be able to determine the compatibility or contradiction of reality and representation while mastering the tasks and principles of media education, the influence of information transmitted in traditional and electronic media formation of practical skills of imagination, information, information attack, information culture and information risk, which are widely and comprehensively studied by the world scientific community today Analyzing the interrelated and harmonious development of such phenomena from a socio-philosophical point of view, forming the skills and competencies of students to apply information correctly in practice, spiritual-ethical, socio-political aspects in the field , the characteristics of the process of harmonization of national and modern values with the reforms carried out in our country, as well as the influence of "mass culture" on our national spirituality consists of a comparative-theoretical research based on scientific evidence.

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